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"A WOMAN OF STRENGTH"

In the deep silence, strength lies hidden,
Even amidst the storms, never ceasing to blossom.

The trials, like waves of the sea,
But her determination, cannot be described.

Each day, new hope she embraces,
Even despite the pains, she continues to walk.

Her heart, like a song,
Of life, full of endless love and joy.

Her dreams, like stars in the sky,
Even in the darkness, continue to shine bright.

Her being, an example to all,
Of persevering, of loving, and of living happily.

Even with the burdens, she remains strong,
Her strength, comes from the inner silence.

Her life, a gift to be cherished,
A woman, who gives inspiration to everyone.